

Ytterbium metal promoted reaction of diselenides with (3-substituted)imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl chlorides

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In the presence of a catalytic amount of methyl iodide, metallic ytterbium promotes the acylation of diselenides with (3-substituted)imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl chlorides to give (3-substituted)imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl selenoesters in good yields under mild and neutral conditions.

Organoselenium compounds have received considerable attention as useful synthetic reagents and intermediates in organic synthesis¹. For example, selenoester are a type of activated esters due to their weak C-Se bond². They are very useful for the synthesis of naturally occurring macrocyclic lactones and lactams³.

A general method for the synthesis of selenoesters is the acylation of selenide anion with acylating reagents⁴. The reductive cleavage of diselenides by metal salts is the important route to give the selenide anion⁵. Taniguchi *et al.*⁶ reported that ytterbium metal could promote the sulfide anion to react with α,β -unsaturated ketons in the presence of benzophenone as catalyst. Recently our group has reported metallic ytterbium promoted reaction of diselenides with allyl bromide⁷.

Here we wish to report a metallic ytterbium promoted reductive reaction of diselenides with 3-(substituted)-imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl chlorides to form (3-substituted)imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl selenoesters in good yields (Scheme 1).

Results and Discussion

The experiment was conducted in THF-HMPA to give the products in good yields. The results are summarized in Table 1. It is seen that without hexamethylphosphoramide

(HMPA) as additive, the results of reactions are not satisfactory even at reflux temperature (Entry 3a, 3g, Table 1).

Table 1. Yb/CH₃I promoted reaction of diselenides with 3-(substituted)imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl chlorides

Compd. no.	R	Ar	Reaction conditions		Yield ^a %
			Time (h)	Temp. (°C)	
3a	H	C ₆ H ₅	4	20–25	76
	H	C ₆ H ₅	4	65–70	58 ^b
b	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4	20–25	77
c	H	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	2	20–25	82
d	H	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	3	20–25	81
e	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	6	20–25	73
f	CH ₃ SO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	4	20–25	77
g	CH ₃ SO ₂	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4	20–25	79
	CH ₃ SO ₂	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4	65–70	60 ^b
h	CH ₃ SO ₂	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	6	20–25	75

^aIsolated yield is based on diselenide and the reaction was carried on in THF-HMPA.

^bWithout the presence of HMPA. All are new compounds.

The results also show that electronic effect in the aromatic ring affects the yields of 3-(substituted)imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl selenoesters. If the substituents on the ring are electron-withdrawing groups the yields are higher than those of electron-donating groups. The possible mechanism is presented in Scheme 2.

Ytterbium metal is activated by CH_3I to give the activated $[\text{Yb}^*]$, which gradually donates three electrons to diselenide to form $[\text{Yb}(\text{SeAr})_3]$ (Scheme 3). As a strong nucleophile, $[\text{Yb}(\text{SeAr})_3]$ reacts with 3-(substituted)-imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl chloride to form 3-(substituted)imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl selenoesters. Without the presence of a catalytic amount of methyl iodide, the reaction cannot occur.

Scheme 3

In summary, ytterbium metal promoted intermolecular reaction of disulfides with 3-(substituted)imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl chlorides provided a facile synthesis of 3-(substituted)imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl selenoesters in good yields under mild and neutral condition.

Experimental

^1H NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*) were recorded on a Bruker AC-80 spectrometer (J value in Hz), chemical shifts being expressed in ppm downfield from internal tetramethylsilane, IR spectra (KBr) on a Bruker-Vector 22 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a HP 5989B spectrometer. Microanalysis was carried out on a Carlo-Erba 1106 instrument. Melting points are uncorrected.

Tetrahydrofuran was distilled from sodium-benzophenone immediately prior to use. Commercial hexamethylphosphoramide was dried over calcium hydride, distilled in vacuum and stored over 4Å molecular sieves. All reactions were carried out under a dry nitrogen atmosphere. Imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl chlorides were prepared according reported method⁸.

General procedure for preparation of 3a-h :

Ytterbium metal (0.173 g, 1 mmol) was first activated with a catalytic amount of methyl iodide (10%). A solution of diselenide (1 mmol) in THF (1 ml) was added by syringe to a brown solution of ytterbium metal in THF-HMPA (11 ml; 10 : 1) at room temperature. An hour later, (3-substituted)-imidazolidin-2-one-1-carbonyl chloride (3 mmol) was added directly to the mixture. After being stirred for a given time, the reaction mixture was quenched with dilute HCl (0.1M) and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 30 ml). The crude product was isolated in the usual way and purified (light yellow crystals) by preparative thin layer chromatog-

raphy using ethyl acetate and cyclohexane (1 : 1) as eluent : **3a**, m.p. 148–150° (Found : C, 44.50; H, 3.88; N, 10.49). $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$ requires : C, 44.62; H, 3.74; N, 10.41%; δ_{H} 3.36 (2H, t, J 10.2), 3.75–3.95 (2H, m), 7.32–7.53 (5H, m), 7.94 (1H, br s); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3240, 3125, 2907, 1734, 1668, 1478, 1402, 1335, 1273, 1065, 1020, 978, 887, 747; m/z (%) 270 (M^+ , 27), 193 (9), 158 (100), 113 (52), 78 (54), 70 (89); **b**, 179–181° (Found : C, 44.03; H, 4.14; N, 9.48). $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Se}$ requires : C, 44.16; H, 4.04; N, 9.36%; δ_{H} 3.38 (2H, t, J 8.5), 3.77–3.97 (5H, m), 6.98 (2H, d, J 8.7), 7.37 (2H, d, J 8.7), 7.92 (1H, br s); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3250, 3133, 2974, 2909, 1722, 1685, 1590, 1494, 1401, 1331, 1248, 1177, 1072, 1020, 891, 823; m/z (%) 300 (M^+ , 19), 188 (63), 172 (8), 113 (18), 108 (100), 70 (45); **c**, 179–180° (Found : C, 39.71; H, 2.85; N, 11.57). $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$ requires : C, 39.56; H, 2.99; N, 11.68%; δ_{H} 3.40 (2H, t, J 8.0), 3.76–3.97 (2H, m), 7.32–7.60 (4H, m), 7.99 (1H, br s); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3225, 3132, 2906, 1738, 1673, 1473, 1405, 1340, 1280, 1087, 1012, 891, 816; m/z (%) 306 (M^+ , 4.7), 304 (M^+ , 12.8), 192 (67), 190 (33), 156 (18), 113 (65), 70 (100); **d**, 152–153° (Found : C, 39.68; H, 2.90; N, 11.56). $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$ requires : C, 39.56; H, 2.99; N, 11.68%; δ_{H} 3.35 (2H, t, J 8.5), 3.77–3.98 (2H, m), 7.41–7.58 (4H, m), 8.02 (1H, br s); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3287, 3081, 2983, 2906, 1718, 1678, 1477, 1400, 1282, 1068, 890, 775, 752, 695; m/z (%) 306 (M^+ , 6.3), 304 (M^+ , 17.1), 192 (61), 190 (31), 156 (16), 113 (100), 70 (92); **e**, 135–137° (Found : C, 46.80; H, 4.16; N, 9.76). $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$ requires : C, 46.65; H, 4.27; N, 9.89%; δ_{H} 2.36 (3H, s), 3.39 (2H, t, J 8.5), 3.75–3.94 (2H, m), 7.19–7.35 (4H, m), 7.93 (1H, br s); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3261, 3137, 3049, 2981, 2906, 1736, 1674, 1478, 1402, 1283, 1069, 890, 753, 697; m/z (%) 284 (M^+ , 19), 172 (74), 113 (27), 91 (100), 70 (65); **f**, 189–190° (Found : C, 37.94; H, 3.60; N, 8.15). $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{SSe}$ requires : C, 38.05; H, 3.48; N, 8.07%; δ_{H} 3.36 (3H, s), 3.89–3.95 (4H, m), 7.40–7.69 (5H, m); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3015, 2933, 1740, 1672, 1480, 1367, 1276, 1244, 1177, 1124, 973, 766, 749, 710, 695; m/z (%) 348 (M^+ , 12), 191 (70), 157 (33), 127 (11), 79 (100); **g**, 166–168° (Found : C, 38.04; H, 3.87; N, 7.51). $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{SSe}$ requires : C, 38.20; H, 3.74; N, 7.43%; δ_{H} 3.36 (3H, s), 3.82 (3H, s), 3.90–3.99 (4H, m), 6.93 (2H, d, J 8.8), 7.47 (2H, d, J 8.8); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3010, 2931, 2838, 1736, 1670, 1588, 1495, 1387, 1353, 1250, 1169, 1122, 966, 816; m/z (%) 378 (M^+ , 24), 191 (54), 187 (56), 127 (11), 79 (100); **h**, 145–147° (Found : C, 39.96; H, 3.78; N, 7.63). $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{SSe}$ requires : C, 39.89; H, 3.91; N, 7.75%; δ_{H} 2.36 (3H, s), 3.35 (3H, s), 3.82–3.93 (4H, m), 7.15–7.40 (4H, m); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3015, 2933, 1720, 1681, 1472, 1398, 1344, 1280, 1167, 1124,

980, 770, 751, 704; *m/z* (%) 362 (M^+ , 12), 191 (67), 171 (24), 127 (12), 91 (50), 79 (100).

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